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Vulnerabilities and disruption risks for the supply chains of Critical Materials necessary for the clean energy transition

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Extended abstract

Faced with the challenge of reducing EU dependence on fossil fuels, especially those imported from Russia, on top of the longstanding climate crisis, the EU has adopted ambitious targets towards accelerating the decarbonisation of its economy and towards net zero emissions by 2050. But, the clean energy transition is a materials transition: Focus is shifting away from the fuels and moving towards the materials which are necessary for manufacturing the clean energy technologies, such as wind turbines, photovoltaic panels, batteries and hydrogen electrolyzers.

In order to meet the EU's energy and climate targets, we need to build the right technologies, in the right quantities, at the right speed. A failure to fulfil these conditions could jeopardise the clean energy transition, delay the decarbonisation of our economy and finally derail EU's efforts to meet its climate targets. However, many of these clean technologies require materials that are imported from just a handful of countries. Most important are the *Critical Raw Materials* (CRM), which are those materials that have significant economic importance and are exposed to a high supply risk, often because of a high concentration of supply from a few third countries. Demand for these precious resources is expected to increase exponentially in the coming years, as not only the EU but also the rest of the world will increasingly rely on renewable energy sources. This combination of import reliance on a small number of third countries on one hand, and the exponential increase of the materials demand on the other, makes the EU *vulnerable to supply disruptions* and elevates the *resilience of the relevant supply chains* to an issue of paramount importance: It is an issue of *Open Strategic Autonomy*.

To secure the undisrupted supply of critical raw materials necessary for the energy and digital transitions and the space and defence agenda, the European Union adopted on 11 April 2024 the [Critical Raw Materials Act](#) (Reg. (2024)1252). The European Commission's Joint Research Centre has studied extensively the materials supply chains of the key strategic technologies, [analysed dependencies](#), bottlenecks and demand projections, and summarised the findings in the report "[Supply chain analysis and material demand forecast in strategic technologies and sectors – a foresight study](#)", which formed a pivotal body of evidence for the development of the Regulation. That study presents a systematic and detailed analysis of the complete supply chains, from raw and processed materials to components, assemblies, super-assemblies and systems, for 15 key technologies across the five strategic sectors of renewables, electro-mobility, decarbonisation of energy intensive industries, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and space and defence.

The study shows a rapid, multi-fold increase in the demand for the critical raw materials, which are key to the EU's green, digital and security goals. For example, compared to 2020, lithium demand for batteries in the EU is expected to grow 12 times as large in 2030 and 21 times as large in 2050. Similarly, the demand for graphite (natural and synthetic), which is used for components of solar and wind industries and batteries, is projected to increase 14 times by 2030 and 26 times by 2050, always compared to 2020 values. And for the rare earth metals (REE) necessary for permanent magnets for wind turbines (NdFeB magnets) a fivefold increase by 2030 is projected.

However, the EU relies heavily on imports for these materials. In fact, for raw materials supply, the EU share in global production is never higher than 7%. For example, while the EU is a global leader in wind turbine production, it is fully dependent on China for the permanent magnets and the rare earth elements used in them. This concentration of supply poses geopolitical risks that needs to be monitored and mitigated. These are among the main objectives of the Regulation.

One important measures for mitigation of risk is through innovation and substitution with advanced material. At the JRC, we are looking closely at the gap between demand and innovation, with a particular focus on high-impact areas and supply chain resilience. We find that [advanced materials can be good for innovation and substitution in many clean energy technologies](#), but they often face barriers to widespread adoption. We need to ensure that more efficient, sustainable alternatives reach the market faster.

In this presentation, we provide insights on the vulnerabilities of selected strategic supply chains, the dependencies and disruption risks on which the EU is exposed, and we discuss how these risks can be assessed, monitored and mitigated, notably through the EU legislative framework of the Critical Raw Materials Act.